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SOFTWARE

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ANNOTATION

This article provides information about computer applications. It talks about the types of computer application software and why they are needed. Each of the applications is discussed separately and detailed information is given about them.

Keywords: *Software, application software, system programs, hardware programs, Microsoft Office programs, programming languages, operating systems, function, resource.*

An application is a specific program, which is designed to solve problems related to a certain problem area. One of the conditions for the effective application of computing techniques in practice is the creation of specialized packages of application programs. Their ease of access and ease of use create conditions for wider application of SSC to engineering work, solving specific tasks in the scientific field, economy, culture, and education [1].

Computer software means a set of programs executed by a computer system. Software is an integral part of a computer and is a logical continuation of hardware. The field of application of a specific computer is determined by the capabilities of the software created for it. Modern computer software can be divided into the following three categories:

Application programs directly ensure the performance of necessary tasks by users.

System programs provide various functions, for example: manage computer resources; makes copies of the information used; monitors the functionality of computer devices; provides information about the computer, etc.

Instrumental programs make it easy to create new programs for computers.

Considering that each of these categories includes thousands of programs, they can be divided into the following groups:

Application software includes: text editors, spreadsheets, graphic editor programs, database management system; integrated software package. Application software includes user-specific problem-specific application programs and application software packages designed for use in a specific problem area.

System software includes: operating systems and shells, testing and diagnostic programs, programs that serve external devices, such as collectors: archivers, antivirus programs.

Instrumental software includes: programming system (translators, part program library, etc.); a programming environment that facilitates the creation or development of programs.

System software and its tasks.

1. From the point of view of information systems, software means a set of software and documentation tools for creating a data processing system with computer tools and using them.

2. From the point of view of computer technology, software means system software that directly supports the operation of computing equipment and a set of "Application software" designed to solve practical problems.

3. General maintenance means implementation of operating systems and maintenance programs.

4. Software packages for the solution of problematic issues are developed and solved on a computer in the provision of special problems. Therefore, any economic process problems are solved through programming systems.

Picture 1. Classification of the software system.

Tasks of system software:

- System utilities. System utilities are designed to service computer hardware, especially carriers, operating systems, and other applications.
- Testing and diagnostic programs. These programs serve to check the performance of the computer and each of its nodes, to identify existing, occurring or potential failures.
- Programs serving collectors. A class of programs designed to serve disk drives and the information stored on them.
- Diagnostic programs identify and eliminate errors in the logical structure of information stored in disk drives.
- Defragmenter software arranges the placement of information on disks in such a way that the maximum speed of accessing or accessing them increases.

Operating system functions.

Operating system (OS) is a set of software tools that manage computer resources, load applications and interact with external devices and other programs, as well as provide user communication with the computer.

An operating system is a program that acts as an intermediary between the user and the computer, serving two purposes: efficient allocation of computer resources and enabling the user to work efficiently.

Computer resources include: processor time, main memory addressable bandwidth, input/output devices, files stored in external memory.

In conclusion, it can be said that computer software is constantly the most used programs. They are used in everyday work related to computers, in all enterprises, even in educational institutions. Because it is impossible to imagine using a computer without software.

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